

Epidemiological and Histological Characteristics of Polyps Detected with Positive Tests During Mass Screening in the Wilaya of Béjaia

Chahira Mazouzi

Medical Oncology University, University Hospital of Béjaia, Algeria

M. Belloul

Gastroenterology University of Bejaia, Algeria

Radia Benyahia

Diagnostic Radiology University, CPMC Algiers, Algeria

Kamel Hail

General Surgery University, Mustapha University Hospital of Algiers, Algeria

Nabil Blik

Medical Nephrology, University of Béjaia, Algeria

N. Laraba

University Hospital of Babeloued Algiers, Algeria

More Information

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Abstract

Detection of polyps during screening colonoscopy has improved significantly in recent years. This results in an increase in the detection rate of adenomas thanks in particular to technological innovations (chromoendoscopy with indigo carmine or electronic) and the training of gastroenterologists, which is inversely correlated with the occurrence of colorectal cancer. The main objective of our study is to describe the epidemiological profile and histological characteristics of polyps and adenomas detected during a mass screening operation for colorectal cancer in a healthy population in the wilaya of Bejaia. The total number of polyps found in our target population is 196 in 89 people. A person can have a minimum of 1 polyp and a maximum of 6 polyps, the average number of polyps per person is 2 polyps, 43% of the population participating in mass screening for colorectal cancer have at least one polyp and 28% have two polyps.

Introduction

Detection of polyps during screening colonoscopy has improved significantly in recent years [1-3]. This results in an increase in the detection rate of adenomas thanks in particular to technological innovations (chromoendoscopy with indigo carmine or electronic) and the training of gastroenterologists, which is inversely correlated with the occurrence of colorectal cancer [4,5]. Therefore, it is essential to best characterize these polyps in order to determine the most appropriate treatment modality (mucosectomy submucosal dissection, surgery) depending on the benign or malignant evolutionary potential of each lesion [6]. Current practice recommends resecting and analyzing all polyps detected during colonoscopy. However, the majority of colorectal polyps detected during a screening colonoscopy are less than 5mm and

the prevalence of “advanced” histological characteristics such as villous nature, high-grade dysplasia or even cancer is very low for these. small polyps (0.5%) [7,8]. Thus, a strategy for selective resection of adenomas with hyperplastic polyps left in place emerged: the concept of “resect and discard” [9]. Recently, a new anatomopathological entity has been identified: serrated polyps [10]. These polyps have a potential to develop into cancer, but their characterization remains difficult given a similar appearance in endoscopy to benign hyperplastic polyps [11]. The concept of the “resect and discard” strategy does not take into consideration this new entity, and it is therefore necessary to improve its per endoscopic identification [12-14]. The main objective of our study is to describe the epidemiological profile and histological characteristics of polyps and adenomas

detected during a mass screening operation for colorectal cancer in a healthy population in the wilaya of Bejaia.

Methods and Patients

During a mass screening for colorectal cancer, we opted for the analysis of the results of the polyps detected, we worked on a non-symptomatic overall population of 4000 citizens in the region of Bejaia, The total number of polyps found in our target population is 196 among 89 people carried out in the Bejaia region.

Results

Number of people with polyps

89(3.5%) people in the population eligible for colorectal mass screening (2686) carry at least one colorectal polyp Number of polyps found.

Table 1: Number of Polyps Detected per Person

Moyenne	2,02 +/- 1,30	
Median	2	
Minimum	1	
Maximum	6	
Percentiles	25%	1
	50%	2
	75%	3
Total	196	

The total number of polyps found in our target population is 196 in 89 people. A person can have a minimum of 1 polyp and a maximum of 6 polyps, the average polyps per person is 2 polyps. Less than 75% of the study population could have 3 polyps. Graph 32 below shows us the frequency of the number of polyps per person.

Chart 1: Number of polyps per person

Macroscopy

43% of the population participating in mass screening for colorectal cancer have at least one polyp and 28% have two polyps, while 2% have 6 polyps. The average size of the polyps found is 10.5 mm +/- 0.96 (range 0.1-70 mm) with a median of 10 mm Concerning the macroscopic appearance, the form most often encountered was pedunculated with a rate of 52.7% (95) followed by sessile forms 38.33% (69) and planar

with a rate of 6.11% (11), Table 31 and 31bis. The polyps found were classified according to size classes with 44.8% of the polyps being less than 1cm in size. 55% of the polyps analyzed have a size > 1cm and 14.9% have a size >= 2 cm, and 45% have a size <=0.99 cm (graph 37). The minimum size of polyps is 1mm and the maximum is 70mm.

Image 1: 6 cm Adenomatous Polyp from a Positive Test in a 57-year-old man Souk Eltenine Bejaia 2018

Table 2: Size of Polyps Found

Moyenne	1,05 +/- 0,96	
Median	1 cm	
Mode	1 cm	
Minimum	0,1 cm	
Maximum	7 cm	
Percentiles	25%	0,5 cm
	50%	1 cm
	75%	1,5 cm

Chart 2: Distribution of Polyps According to Their Sizes

Distribution of Polyps According to Age Groups of the Population Studied

There is a significant difference between the frequencies of polyps according to the age groups of the study population; the peak frequency is located at 35% of polyps found in people aged between 60-64 years $P=0.02$ ($\alpha=0.05$) graph 34. There are no differences between the frequencies of polyps between the two sexes. 29% of polyps are located in the sigmoid, and 26% are located in the right part of the colon,

Chart 3: Distribution of Polyps According to the Age of the Population

Chart 4: Distribution of Polyps by Sex

Topography of polyps

The polyps detected are located first in the sigmoid with a rate of 29%, then in the right colon with a rate of 26%, and also in the rectum and the left colon with a rate of 20%. They are rarely observed in other segments of the colon.

Chart 6: Distribution of Polyps According to the Paris Classification (%)

37% of the polyps found are adenomas out of the 182 analyzed, (14)7% of polyps not found, (10) 5.1% lost during colonoscopy and (4)2% not found after histological analysis while 63 % are non-adenomatous polyps.

Chart 7: Distribution of polyps according to their histological aspects

Table 3: Number of people with adenomas

Adenoma	Persons atteintes de polypes	Population avec test+	Population participante
Non	(56) 63%	(184) 84,8%	(2652) 98,7%
Oui	(33) 37%	(33) 15,2%	(33) 1,3%
Total	(89) 100%	(217) 100%	(2685) 100%

37% of people in the population with polyps have at least one Adenoma and 15% of the population with test+ have at least one adenoma, while 1.3% of the participating population has at least one adenoma. 30% of adenomas with test+ have villous type adenomas, 20% of adenomas are tubulo -villous, and 50% have tubular adenomas.

Chart 8: Distribution of Polyps According to their Sizes

Chart 9: Distribution of Polyps According to the Age of the Population

Chart 10: Topography of Polyps

Chart 11: Distribution of Polyps According to the Paris Classification (%)

Table 4: Number of people with adenomas

Adenoma	Persons atteintes de polypes	Population avec test+	Population participante
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Oui	(33) 37%	(33) 15,2%	(33) 1,3%
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Graph 12: Distribution of Histological Types of Adenomas According to the Age of the Population with Test +

Graph 13: Distribution of Histological Types of Adenomas According to Their Sizes among Adenomas

Table 5: Histological Type of Adenomas According to Their Sizes and Degrees of Dysplasia in People with at Least One Adenoma

Signe de dysplasie	Type d'adénome	Classe de taille			Total
		<=0,99cm	1-1,99 cm	>=2 cm	
Non	TUBULEUX	0	0	1	1
	TUBULEUX VILLEUX	1	0	0	1
	Total	1	0	1	2
Haut	VILLEUX	2	4	4	10
	TUBULEUX	0	4	2	6
	TUBULEUX VILLEUX	1	4	1	6
Total		3	12	7	22
Bas	VILLEUX	0	3	0	3
	TUBULEUX	1	1	1	3
	TUBULEUX VILLEUX	3	0	0	3
Total		4	4	1	9
Total	VILLEUX	2	7	4	13
	TUBULEUX	1	5	4	10
	TUBULEUX VILLEUX	5	4	1	10

Discussion

Advanced adenomas The detection rate for advanced adenomas is defined as the proportion of patients in whom an advanced adenoma is the most negative lesion detected, among those who have performed an analyzable screening test. It is expressed per 1,000 people screened. The overall detection rate of advanced adenomas is 14.7%. Among advanced adenomas, 13/33 people with adenoma have at least one adenoma with a villous histological type; 22/33 people with adenoma have at least one high-grade dysplasia adenoma; 25/33 people with adenoma have at least one adenoma larger than 1 cm; 142 8/33 people with adenoma have at least one adenoma larger than 1 cm and a villous histological type with a high grade of dysplasia at the same time (Table 5). The detection of advanced adenomas is more frequent in men: 63% in men compared to 37% in women. The detection rate of advanced adenomas increases with the age of the patients. Let us compare our results with other pilot

studies of the organized colorectal cancer screening: in the French study, this rate was 4.4% across all pilot experiments, but departmental variations were recorded between 2.3% and 18% (174). Illustrated comparisons of the results of adenoma detection rates and advanced adenomas from pilot studies carried out in Australia, Thailand, and England. TDA is proven to be a major indicator of colorectal cancer prevention; % of the TDA allows a 3% reduction in the risk of interval cancer which must remain the fear of every gastroenterologist Figure 1 The TDA is set in each country by expert endoscopists in association with anatomopathologists. To date in Algeria, no minimum rate is set for diagnostic endoscopies or for follow-up. The DOCCR program is newly introduced and a TDA must be set in the very near future, our results remain insufficient on this point (TDA = 17.5%) and research work is necessary for the success of the CRC screening program.

Figure 1: TDA of 71 Alsatian Endoscopists for Tests+

Conclusion

Colorectal polyps are very common in the general population. The diagnosis is made by endoscopy. The morphological study of the polyp is fundamental in order to determine the technique to be used to perform the resection (loop, EMR, ESD). TEM offers an alternative to radical surgery for large rectal polyps and rectal tumors with low risk of lymph node invasion. Lymphatic invasion, submucosal invasion ≥ 1 mm, tumor budding or poor tumor differentiation are the four main determinants of lymph node invasion. In case of high risk (30 to 40%), radical surgery is recommended. Monitoring must be adapted to the type of polyp, the number and size as well as the presence or absence of a carcinomatous component.

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